

The Theory of Segmental Units and Changes in the Digital Environment in Russian and Uzbek Internet Communication

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Annotation: The article examines the problems and specific features of Internet communication. It highlights the significant influence of informational components on society and the individual. As a result, information as a value of a new type of society is defined not only, and not so much, by its mass character or accessibility, or by its economic or political potential, but rather by its capacity for personalization, which provides its possessor with new dimensions of self-identification. This capacity is most fully realized in computer-mediated communication via the internet. The transformation of linguistic personality, accompanied by the formation of a virtual worldview, including a linguistic one, reflects life within the internet space with its specific characteristics.

Key words: the Internet, communication, sociality, a person, slang, emojis, the virtual worldview, word formation, phonetics, graphology, the lexicological level and phraseology.

Introduction.

Modern society is characterized by the rapid development of digital technologies, which have a significant impact on language communication. The Internet has become the most important platform for communication among millions of users, leading to the emergence of new forms of verbal interaction. Analyzing the phenomenon of the Internet, Umberto Eco noted that “our societies will soon split (or have already split) into two classes: those who only watch television, that is, receive ready-made images and ready-made judgments about the world without the right to critically select

information, and those who look at a computer screen, who are capable of selecting and processing information.” [4, p. 7]

The widespread use of the Internet has led to the emergence of an entirely new information community, where a person sitting in front of a computer not only immerses themselves in a special communicative space, virtual in its ontology, but can also actively express themselves within it, shaping and transforming it. Thus, with the help of a computer and immersion into the world of the Internet, modern individuals create a new environment for their existence and a new form of social interaction with other people and with the world as a whole.

The problems and peculiarities of Internet communication have attracted the attention of scholars since the late twentieth century. According to E. P. Belinskaya, as expressed in her work “The Internet and the Identity Structures of Personality”: “The preference for analyzing Internet research is also due to the fact that it most fully embodies the leading feature of modern information technologies, namely their interactive nature.”

Main Part.

Segmental units are elements of language that are arranged sequentially in the speech chain: phonemes, syllables, morphemes, words, and phrases. Internet communication is characterized by a high speed of information exchange, informal interaction, the use of multimedia tools, and the reduction of linguistic structures.

In Russian Internet discourse, anglicisms, abbreviations, and graphic modifications of words are actively used. A distinctive feature of Uzbek Internet communication is the use of both the Latin and Cyrillic alphabets, as well as the active borrowing of English and Russian vocabulary.

Both languages demonstrate tendencies toward abbreviation, borrowing, and the adaptation of linguistic means to the digital environment.

And this opportunity is most fully represented in computer-mediated communication through the Internet.

Indeed, in the 21st century, thanks to the development of the World Wide Web, people gain access to virtually any information. They can filter it according to their interests, leave comments, provide their own arguments, and, most importantly, share their experience and knowledge.

Today, Internet communication is an integral part of modern society. Internet communication is understood as computer-mediated interaction between two or more individuals, characterized by the invisibility of communicators, the written form of messages, the possibility of immediate feedback, as well as interaction through the exchange of electronic messages or mutual exchange and access to information stored on the communicators' computers.

In recent years, the functioning of the Russian language on the global Internet has been studied by many linguists. Changes in linguistic identity occur simultaneously with the formation of a virtual worldview, including a linguistic one, reflecting life in the Internet space with its specific features. All of this significantly influences the linguistic situation and requires serious linguistic research.

It is quite possible that we are witnessing the formation of a new style in the Russian language—the style of Internet communication—whose distinctive features include written pronunciation, hyperintertextuality, and recorded colloquial speech. At the same time, a qualitatively new feature of this style is its spontaneity despite its written form. Researchers in different countries observe and study similar processes occurring in natural national languages used by Internet users. For example, even in England, where Internet terminology is not borrowed from a foreign language, scholars have recognized the need to identify and study a new functional style called “Weblish” (Web + English).

Today, it is an indisputable fact that the Internet is the greatest source of information known to humanity. However, its capabilities allow it to be used not only as a tool for acquiring knowledge but also as a means of communication.

The transformation of individual consciousness on the Internet, along with the formation of a new network-based lifestyle and way of thinking, significantly affects the linguistic situation.

Slang is a set of special words or new meanings of existing words used within various human communities (professional, social, age-related, etc.). It is necessary to distinguish slang from colloquial and nonstandard expressions.

In ordinary speech, such words are used to intensify the emotional coloring of an utterance. Words that serve as milder substitutes for other words are not considered slang but are classified as euphemisms.

According to V. S. Matyushenkov, slang is a historically developed variant of linguistic norms existing primarily in oral speech and functionally distinct from jargon and professional elements of language.

Slang consists of words that are often regarded as violations of the norms of the standard language. These are highly expressive and ironic words used to denote objects and phenomena discussed in everyday life. What distinguishes computer slang from other types of slang?

Analyzing the accumulated information on this issue, it can be said that when studying computer slang, we are dealing with a synthesis of four groups of words:

professionalisms, vulgarisms, jargonisms, and slangisms proper.

Firstly, these words serve as a means of communication among people of the same profession—programmers or simply individuals who use computers for similar purposes. In this case, such words function as synonyms for English professional terms while differing from them in emotional coloring.

Secondly, computer slang is distinguished by the fact that it is confined to the realities of the computer world. The slang terms under consideration refer exclusively to this sphere, thereby separating it from everything else and often remaining incomprehensible to people unfamiliar with the field.

Thirdly, this vocabulary frequently includes rather vulgar words.

When communicating on social networks, 80% of respondents allow the use of abbreviations, 66% use slang, and 66% employ nonstandard vocabulary in interactive communication (see Diagram 1).

A new form of speech is emerging on the Internet—formally written but conceptually oral-written (less structured, “telegraphic,” and containing elements of spoken language). It is referred to in various ways as “written colloquial speech,” “computer-mediated speech,” “Internet speech,” “cyberlanguage,” “netspeak,” “weblish,” “netlish,” “electronic language,” or “electronic discourse.”

The Latinization of Cyrillic is closely connected with the influence of the English language on Russian and with Americanization.

Syntactic structures are becoming more fragmented, and formal syntactic connections are weakening. These connections become freer and are often not formally expressed. Ellipsis and various types of truncation are common. Utterances become shorter, and their content is simplified.

At the lexical and word-formation levels, the tendency toward simplification manifests itself in compressed word formation and abbreviation:

- 1) The creation of abbreviations by omitting vowels (e.g., “спс,” “спсб,” “плз,” “плжста”).
- 2) The emergence of letter abbreviations consisting of the initial letters of phrases or statements (e.g., BTW, OMG). These phenomena include not only forms borrowed from English but also occasional abbreviations created by analogy in Russian, such as

“TIMCM” (“in my humble opinion”) and “ЕМНИИП” (“if my memory serves me correctly”).

3) The formation of abbreviations (acronyms) consisting of letters and numbers based on similarity in pronunciation between letters, numbers, and words (e.g., “про100” = simply, “4ë” = what?, “05” = again, “1очество” = loneliness). These forms are borrowed from English-language practices.

4) Forms created through regressive derivation, often ignoring morphemic boundaries (e.g., inet, vinch, proga, moder, admin, infa, distr). There are also combinations of univerbation and derivation (e.g., real, virt, lichka).

The increasing complexity of orthographic, punctuation, and typographic means serves the following purposes:

- 1) Compensation for the paralinguistic component of communication;
- 2) The expression of various pragmatic intentions (for example, the creation of emoticons using keyboard symbols to convey different emotions; their presence in a text is often regarded as a sign of informality or lack of seriousness), such as :) or :-(;
- 3) The individualization of speech and the creation of language play.

The use of ellipses as a means of expressing uncertainty, incompleteness, an emotional pause, the passage of time, or the segmentation of a text into several fragments:

“Ecstasy pills are great, of course..... but I prefer amphetamines.....; You take a pill and after 20 minutes a warm wave washes over you... you can physically feel your pupils dilating... your skin becomes soft and everyone around seems so wonderful!”, “It’s amazing to go outside on a warm sunny day and walk on the grass... as if barefoot...”; Multiple repetition of the same letter reflects the semantic significance of information: “crazyyyyyyyyyyyyyy”;

Highlighting words and entire sentences with CAPITAL LETTERS: “THEY ARE ALL AWESOME!)))”, “Could it be that they actually have a HIDDEN meaning?”.

This may indicate a raised voice or emphasis on a particular word;

The use of a capital letter instead of a lowercase one when it carries semantic meaning or when the communicator seeks an unambiguous interpretation of the statement: “Do you write with MiStakeS or without MiStakes?”;

The use of brackets, symbols (the “+” sign may indicate a positive evaluation, agreement, or support for something or someone; the “=” sign may mean “as a result,” “is the same as,” or “corresponds to”), as well as boldface and underlining.

The lexical level of Internet communication is characterized by a large number of English-language elements, active word-formation processes, genre differentiation of units according to various communication situations (chat, forum, e-mail, etc.), as well as processes of argotization and jargonization, an example of which is the so-called “Padonki argot.” All this indicates the dynamic development of the language of Internet communication.

“Horizon is tilted” is a professional expression referring to a common mistake made by novice photographers when the horizon line in a photograph appears slanted. The meme originated from criticism of a photograph posted on one of the websites. It is used either to criticize a poor-quality photograph or as an ironic apology by the author for the quality of a photograph.

“Lick the socket” is a meme that originated thanks to the television series “Wonderfalls,” which contains the phrase “Lick the lightswitch.” In Russian translation, it became “lick the switch.” It is used when a speaker wants to say, “Leave me alone, I’m tired of you already,” or to express a negative evaluation of someone or something.

Conclusion. During the study of written Internet communication, it was observed that users most often ignore established spelling and punctuation norms. The digital environment has a significant influence on the development of linguistic units and the

formation of new communication models.

Deviation from norms in Internet communication texts is caused by various factors, including:

- 1) insufficient mastery of spelling norms;
- 2) the peculiarities of recording text using a keyboard, during which the holistic image of a word or sentence is broken down into separate fragments;
- 3) lack of time and/or simultaneous communication with other users;
- 4) demonstration of belonging to a particular group of users who possess a special language;
- 5) the use of language play (for example, carnivalization or the creation of a virtual persona).

During the course of the work, conclusions of practical value for the present day were formulated. In particular, based on the analysis of text messages, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. In Internet communication, the most common lexical forms are abbreviations, namely acronyms.
2. All acronyms used in communication can be classified according to their meaning and function into acronyms expressing opinions, emotions and evaluations, greetings and farewells, computer terminology, and electronic correspondence.
3. In the process of communication, syllables, words, phrases, and even entire sentences are graphically replaced by numbers.
4. In modern acronyms, the phonetic form of the digit 1 (one) coincides with the syllable or word “one” and “won”; the digit 2 (two) coincides with the words and syllables “to” and “too”; the digit 8 (eight) phonetically and graphically replaces parts of many words and syllables such as “ate” and “eat”; the digit 4 (four) replaces the preposition “for”.

5. In the process of communication, a special language has developed that is characterized by the widespread use of abbreviations. In this case, we are dealing not only with a method of communication through short messages, but also with a new international language distinguished by simplicity, a flexible attitude toward norms and traditions, emotional expressiveness, and extensive use of abbreviations.
6. The tendency toward the economy of linguistic means is universal and is determined by the needs of human thinking and communication, namely, the desire to express the diversity of the objective world, with its complex connections and relationships between objects and phenomena, as economically as possible through semantically rich but formally shorter signs.
7. With the expansion of the Internet user audience in recent years, the process of adapting English abbreviations to Russian linguistic patterns has become increasingly active.

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